

D3.2 European Smart Tourism Tools Observatory

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Executive Summary

This report describes the methodology and results used to build the first version of the European Online Observatory on Smart Tourism Tools (STT), as well as the development status of WP3 / Task 3.2 of the RESETTING project.

The first section presents the work carried out to reach an agreed definition of Smart Tourism Tools, a brief presentation of studies related to the topic, a presentation of the methodology used and a discussion of the results obtained.

The results of the work carried out made it possible to generate a consensual definition of STT and to extract the main variables, considering their relative weight, that make up an STT. These results make it possible to construct a Smartness index that will classify the offer showcased in the Observatory. This phase is currently being finalized.

The methodology used to develop the European Smart Tourism Tools Observatory is then presented. It includes two specific fields: web mining and smart extraction, transformation and load of textual data from STT descriptions, supported by Large Language Models and traditional data processing methods; and the development and implementation of the platform that makes up the observatory.

This first version of the Observatory is populated with STT from one major international catalogue, but it does not include yet the calculation of the Smartness index, as this is dependent on the completion of the consensual STT definition task.

This report concludes with some considerations about the dissemination and maintenance of the Observatory.

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Terminology and Acronyms

<i>API</i>	<i>Application Programming Interface</i>
<i>CoT</i>	<i>Chain-of-Thought</i>
<i>EC</i>	<i>European Commission</i>
<i>ENTER</i>	<i>The e-Tourism Conference of the International Federation for IT and Travel & Tourism</i>
<i>ETL</i>	<i>Extract, Transform and Load</i>
<i>EU</i>	<i>European Union</i>
<i>FP</i>	<i>Framework Programme</i>
<i>IACuDiT</i>	<i>International Conference of the International Association of Cultural and Digital Tourism</i>
<i>ICOTTS</i>	<i>International Conference on Tourism Technology & Systems</i>
<i>IoT</i>	<i>Internet of Things</i>
<i>LLM</i>	<i>Large Language Model</i>
<i>LNP</i>	<i>Natural Language Processing</i>
<i>MAXQDA</i>	<i>software for computer-assisted qualitative and mixed methods data, text, and multimedia analysis</i>
<i>PMB</i>	<i>Project Management Board</i>
<i>PMP</i>	<i>Project Management Plan</i>
<i>SEGITTUR</i>	<i>Spanish Secretary of State for Tourism</i>
<i>ST</i>	<i>Smart Tourism</i>
<i>STT</i>	<i>Smart Tourism Tools</i>
<i>STAB</i>	<i>Scientific and Technical Advisory Board</i>
<i>STD</i>	<i>Smart Tourism Destination</i>
<i>ToT</i>	<i>Tree of Thoughts</i>
<i>WP</i>	<i>Work Package</i>

1. Introduction / Motivation

There is no "uptake of digitalisation, innovation and new technologies in tourism" if there is no supply of Smart Tourism Tools (STTs). Therefore, it is of utmost importance to have an observatory to monitor the current status, both on the supply and demand side, and to check how things are (hopefully) improving throughout the duration of this project. We will use web mining techniques to characterize supply and survey techniques during the various rounds of SME selection for funding to characterize demand.

STTs have the power to optimize the efficiency and sustainability of tourism operations, but the wide variety of technological solutions, past experiences and lessons learned require a thoughtful and systematic approach to identifying the appropriate technological solutions and the principles they must follow to achieve the desired outcomes.

We believe that there is a mismatch between the supply and demand of STTs for SMEs, probably due to their financial and technical limitations. It is important to characterize this supply, as some STTs may be appropriate for SMEs and others may not. We will propose a pragmatic but sound taxonomy to characterize STTs. This taxonomy will be used to classify all European STTs found.

The number of European STTs found, classified according to the proposed taxonomy and available in the online observatory, is a good measure of the representativeness of the sample. In the RESETTING proposal, we proposed a performance indicator of 30 STTs as a minimum level of representativeness of the European STT supply.

This document describes the methodology used to build the first version of the European Online Observatory of STTs.

2. STT Taxonomy

2.1 Related work

The operationalization of Smart Tourism (ST) is supported by the development and implementation of STT, supported by different technologies and operating in different domains.

Dejan et al. [Krizaj et al., 2021] analyzed a set of 35 publicly available descriptions of ST projects implemented in Europe (from an initial list of 352 potentially relevant projects). The authors pose several research questions to determine what is really being implemented in destinations that call themselves 'smart' and whether most projects branded as 'smart' actually qualify as such. The authors also analyze the content of ST projects currently implemented in Europe and supported by EU funding, their characteristics, and the technological solutions used, and whether they show rapid technological progress in tourism services. They also sought to determine what these projects can tell us about the future of ST and STD. The study found that "the vast majority of projects labeled as 'smart' mainly pursue environmental sustainability goals, but do not feature advanced technology that meets the criteria of the Smart Actionable Attributes, and do not address social sustainability issues to the same extent as environmental ones". This suggests that there is a disconnect between the buzz generated by smartness in tourism and its actual implementation at the destination level. They use Buhalis's [Buhalis, 2022] definition of smart systems in tourism - "*Smart systems use a wide range of networks, connected devices, sensors, and algorithms to provide big data through the IoT*" - to define **Smart Actionable** attributes used to categorize ST projects: i) **networked/connected devices and applications**, ii) coordinated by **intelligent algorithms**, iii) based on collected and analyzed information at a **big data** level. The authors classified the above 35 projects into the following groups, based on their technology type and Smart Actionable:

- **Group 1** consists of projects that have been assigned the **networked/connected** and **Big Data** attributes and deal with large amounts of networked and connected data. The **intelligent algorithms** attribute is negligible in this group. The technology types most represented in this group are sensors, networks, and IoT.
- **Group 2** consists of projects that are fully connected only by the **networked/connected** attribute and use networked and connected data, but not in large quantities. The **intelligent algorithms** attribute is less frequent in this group. The **Big Data** attribute is not present at all (although the projects most commonly use sensors, the data collected is not rich enough to place the projects in the Big Data

category). The most common technology types in this group are sensors and mobile applications.

- **Group 3** consists of projects that are only associated with the **Big Data** attribute and do not address **networked/connected** goals and rarely use **intelligent algorithms** in data processing.
- **Group 4** consists of projects that have not been assigned to any Smart Actionable type and use significantly fewer individual technology types. The most represented technology types are mobile applications and sensors. These projects are presented and promoted as smart, but on closer inspection do not meet these standards and guidelines. Such projects accounted for 31% of all projects in the analysis.

Buhalis and Amaranggana [Buhalis and Amaranggana, 2015] discovered 3 different moments in the personalized services expected by tourists in STD:

1. Before Trip: To support the planning phase by providing all relevant real-time information based on user profiling to make a more informed decision;
2. During Trip: Enhanced access to real-time information to help tourists explore the destination, direct personalized services, and real-time feedback loop;
3. After Trip: Prolonged engagement to relive the experience, as well as an appropriate feedback system that allows tourists to review their holistic tourism experience.

Several initiatives have been developed to gather information on STTs. In Europe, we highlight the Scottish Tourism Toolkit [Gidlund and McGurran, 2020], the European Commission's report on ST Practices [Scholz & Friends Agenda, 2022], and SEGITTUR (Spanish Secretary of State for Tourism)'s Catalogue of Technological Solutions for STD [SEGITTUR Turismo e Innovación, 2022].

2.2 Proposed STT assessment framework

The proposed STT assessment framework, which takes into account contributions to the sustainability of tourism, is described in this section.

2.2.1 Introduction

In order to properly understand ST (offer), a preliminary literature review on the ST concept and on the STT concept, and an extensive online search on existing STTs were carried out. These initial efforts revealed two significant research gaps, or rather research uncertainties:

- ST as a concept is poorly defined, often linked to the concept of Smart Cities;
- STTs are often just claims based on technological aspects provided by developers; the "smartness" of such technologies is often difficult to assess.

In addition, the term "smart" is used to describe developments driven by cutting-edge technologies, and as technological development is constantly evolving, STT is a moving target where a "smart" offer quickly becomes a "dumb" one.

The RESETTING project Task 3.2 (European STT Observatory) aims to provide a broad overview of the supply of Smart Tourism Tools (STT) in Europe. To populate this Observatory, a methodology and tools are needed to assess the "smartness" of the European tourism offer, based on a sound definition of Smart Tourism (ST) and STT in particular. Consequently, it was clear that we needed a consensual definition of ST and an objective, adaptable definition of STT to fulfill the objective of Task 3.2.

2.2.2 Towards a consensual definition of Smart Tourism (Tools)

In order to achieve a consensual definition of STT and to create a robust taxonomy for ST that can cope with technological evolution, we used a scientific collaborative approach, inviting experts to provide their views.

- *Methodology- Questionnaire*

We created a form-based web application with the following principles in mind:

- be intuitive and easy to answer;
- have no mandatory answers;
- provide help content;
- be engaging with a game-like feel to encourage answering in all areas;
- provide motivational quotes as responding progresses;
- reward respondents who answer all the questions with a prize: a virtual tourism experience;
- do not collect personal data;

- be able to capture both the conceptual and technological aspects derived from the literature review using "closed type" questions, but also allow for the introduction of open content;
- allow users to provide textual definitions in an open question, and to leave comments and/or personal information if desired;
- allow users from different countries to view and respond to the survey in their native language.

Next, we briefly present the web-app GUI explaining how answering is achieved.

The first question was about where the focus of STT should be in terms of the nexus: Tourist - Destination - Tourism Operator; and Sustainability - Technology. The respondents were asked to drag the icon to the desired area in the Venn diagram (see Figure 1). Regarding these questions, we later identified an error in the formulation of the Venn diagram related to the nexus - Sustainability - Technology: the chosen approach does not allow users to select the individual intersections between {Society, Technology} and {Environment, Economy} that are hidden behind higher-level central intersections.

Fig. 1: STT focus

The second question on the technologies that make up STT asks users to rate the "smartness" of the technologies most commonly identified in STT offer (see Figure 2).

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What is your concept of Smart Tourism?

Completeness (%) 0 50 100

Background STT focus **Technologies** Fundamental principles Your definition Submit

#2 Please rank the technologies based on their cutting edge status

Drag the technologies to the rank boxes in the right.
Cutting Edge status increases from bottom to top.
Each rank row can have as many technologies as you want.

Don't know a tech? Drag it here!

or delete rank rows by clicking .
 Add new technologies by clicking the button below.
 Delete created technologies by dragging and dropping it over .

QR Code Virtual Reality Drones A.I.
 Data Analytics Bluetooth WiFi 3G/4G
 5G/6G Image Video Social Media
 Web dev App dev IoT Gamification
 Sensors Audio Edge Computers Beacons
 Data Visualisation Augmented Reality

Smart technologies

I don't think this is a STT at all!

Dumb technologies

Fig. 2: STT technologies

The third question, on the basic principles of ST (see Figure 3), asks respondents to compare different concepts underlying the definition of ST derived from the literature review.

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What is your concept of Smart Tourism?

Completeness (%) 0 50 100

Background STT focus Technologies **Fundamental principles** Your definition Submit

#3 Rank the sentences below, dragging them into the boxes on the right, to achieve a ranking of perceived importance.

STT are tools that:

- Tailor the tourist experience to each specific user needs.
- Enhance the tourist's emotional, sensorial and/or cognitive experience.
- Contribute to the tourist socio-cultural enrichment.
- Can influence tourist consumption decisions.
- Bring new opportunities to environmental, responsible, and accessible tourism.
- Improve the social aspects of the touristic destination.
- Improve the environmental status of the touristic destination.
- Improve the economy of the touristic destination.
- Promote the touristic destination.
- Improve tourism companies' competitiveness.
- Foster the creation of innovative touristic offers.
- Improve marketing effectiveness.
- Simplify tourism companies' operations.
- Scaffold tourism companies' decision making.
- Generate input data for tourism management stakeholders.
- Use cutting-edge technology.
- Use mainstream technologies in innovative ways.

Smart Tourism Tools

I don't think this sentence characterizes STT at all!

Other Tourism Tools

Fig. 3: ST principles

In both questions 2 and 3, users are asked to rank the given hypotheses by dragging them into the desired box. Users can place multiple items in each rank box and add or remove rank levels at will to allow for a more discriminating separation of alternatives. In addition, users can also create and rank their own technologies and/or principles.

The fourth and final question is an open-ended question where users can enter their own definition of ST(T).

- Methodology- Respondents

The population of interest for our survey is the community of ST experts. In order to maximize the chances of obtaining a large number of respondents, we searched the following databases for papers containing the term 'smart tourism' in the title, abstract and/or keywords, and for the contact details of their authors: [Scopus](#), [SpringerLink](#), [WebOfScience](#), [lens.org](#), [Dimensions](#), and [Scielo](#).

In addition, since experts in a given field usually meet with their peers to validate their findings and to inspire themselves through discussion, we also retrieved the contacts of the authors of papers presented at the following annual events focused on ST topics:

- The e-Tourism Conference of the International Federation for IT and Travel & Tourism ([ENTER](#))
- International Conference of the International Association of Cultural and Digital Tourism ([IACuDIT](#))
- International Conference on Tourism Technology & Systems ([ICOTTS](#))

We sent a personalized email to each of the identified ST experts, inviting them to participate in the survey. In June 2023, due to a change in the services purchased from Google, we stopped collecting responses. Although the collection of contributions is no longer active, the tool can be consulted [through this link](#)¹.

- Results - presentation and analysis

We received 334 expert responses worldwide, with an average completion rate of 82% (measured within the web application itself). The web application's built-in completeness checker measures the partial completeness of each question, meaning that if a respondent fails to rank a given variable in a ranking question, they will not receive a full score. Looking at completeness based on whether the question was answered or not, the average completeness rises to 91% (see Table 1). Note that the average shown is based on the variables originally provided (excluding respondents' own variables) and also excludes

¹ If you answer all the questions, there is no need to do it thoroughly, as we do not collect the answers, you can still check out our prize. Be sure to click on the red gem after you click on submit. To enjoy the prize, please note the red arrows, since they are a bit dim.

responses to additional comments and contact information. These exclusions were also applied in the web application's completeness checker, as these variables represent additional information to the survey.

Table 1: Average form completeness

Question	% of responses
STT focus: tourist, destination, company	92%
STT focus: sustainability, technology	93%
Rank tool custom user STT definitions	2%
STT definition rank	95%
Rank tool custom user technologies	10%
Technologies rank	95%
Respondent STT definition	81%
Respondent comments	25%
Email contact information	61%
Average completeness	91%

In terms of global representativeness, we received responses from 52 countries (see Figure 4), although the true global representativeness may be higher as the geo-referencing is based on the (optional) email domains provided, meaning that only 47% of the responses could be geo-referenced. In addition, 29 of the responses were in 10 different languages other than English - Greek, Korean, Spanish, Italian, Slovak, Chinese (simplified), Ukrainian, Portuguese, Polish and Persian.

Fig. 4: Worldwide distribution of responses

Figure 5 shows the results of the answers to question #1, concerning the focus of STT.

Fig. 5: Tourist-Operator-Destination responses

Visual analysis of the diagram regarding the Tourist-Operator-Destination nexus shows a consensus of the STT focus on the tourist and the destination to the detriment of the tourism operator. Further analysis of the diagram seems to indicate that the users' perception of the data collection method was not consistent across the universe of STT experts. As the data collection approach is innovative, this may be the case. It is reasonable to assume that the problem under study should be additive, i.e. the intersections of the groups should have higher values (or at least the same order of magnitude) than the independent groups, i.e. if one group, let's say 'Tourist', is key to STT, then intersections containing 'Tourist' should retain at least part of that importance and add the importance of the intersecting group, although the importance of each independent group in the intersected group could be different from their importance in the independent groups. To overcome this and perform a deeper analysis of the data, and ultimately extract indicators for the Smart Index, we analyzed the data considering that each level of intersection has a separate universe. In this way, we can derive the relative importance of each of the nexus elements within each intersection universe.

If we assume that the participants responding in the dual intersection universe use intrinsic importance (weight) for each of the base variables - Tourist, Destination, Company - when answering, this means that an average ponderation can be calculated for each of these variables within the dual intersection universe.

This can be expressed as:

$$Result_i = \alpha \cdot Tourist + \beta \cdot Destination + \gamma \cdot Company \quad (eq. 1)$$

where:

i is the group of all possible intersections in that universe. In the case of the dual intersection universe - [Destination_Tourist, Tourist_Company, Company_Destination],

α , β , and γ represent the weights of the base variables - Tourist, Destination, Company -, constant within the intersection universe.

Using eq.1 we can create a system of equations for each of the groups in a given universe. Note that for the dual intersection universe eq.1 only has two terms.

We can then create a matrix for the equation system - A - taking '1/2' for each of the base variables present in each dual intersection world, as we are only analyzing dual intersections.

$$\begin{array}{c}
 [A] \quad \times \quad [X] = [B] \\
 \left| \begin{array}{ccc} 0.5 & 0.5 & 0 \\ 0.5 & 0 & 0.5 \\ 0 & 0.5 & 0.5 \end{array} \right| \times \left| \begin{array}{c} \alpha \\ \beta \\ \gamma \end{array} \right| = \left| \begin{array}{c} 0.50 \\ 0.29 \\ 0.21 \end{array} \right| \quad (\text{eq. 2})
 \end{array}$$

where:

A is the systems equation matrix,

X is the matrix of weights α , β , and γ , that we are trying to find, and

B is the matrix containing the ratio of dual intersection i , over the total of the dual intersections universe, calculated directly from the gathered data.

We can then solve for X :

$$X = A^{-1} \cdot B \quad (\text{eq. 3})$$

where

A^{-1} is the inverted matrix for the equation system.

X contains the average intrinsic weights of the universe of the double intersection. We can directly estimate the average intrinsic weights for the independent universe by calculating the ratio of the entries in each independent group to the total entries for the independent universe. The average weights of the whole universe - independent & intersecting - can then be estimated using a weighted average, taking into account the dimensions of each universe in the data collected.

Table 2: Average weights Tourist-Operator-Destination nexus

Tourist	Destination	Company
0.50	0.42	0.08

Table 2 shows the resulting overall weights for the Tourist-Operator-Destination nexus. It is clear, as identified in the visual analyses, that the Tourist is the most important focus for STT, closely followed by the Destination, and the Tour Operator (Company) is not as central to STT. We can then apply these averages to each group by adding the weights of the variables present in each group. Figure 6 presents the results in a Venn diagram to facilitate comparison with the data collected (Figure 5). As you can see, the relationships of the original data remain, but now we have the cumulative effect required by raising the levels of intersection.

Fig. 6: Tourist-Operator-Destination results

With regard to the Sustainability-Technology nexus, as mentioned above, the approach used to collect data in this particular Venn diagram does not allow the user to select the intersections between {Society, Technology} and {Environment, Economy}. However, it is important to note that although the user cannot enter data at the two intersections mentioned, the graphical nature of the response method leads the user to spatially locate their responses in the regions closest to their intended focus. This means that it is still possible to draw valid conclusions from the data collected.

A visual analysis of this diagram (see Fig. 7) shows that the focus is on the environment, society, and technology, and their combinations, to the detriment of the economy. Two

interesting conclusions can be drawn from this. Firstly, although the term "smart" is intertwined with technology, at least in the field of SST, the emphasis seems to be primarily on the environment and society, and only then on technology. Secondly, technology seems to bypass one of the pillars of the tripartite concept of sustainability, the economy.

Fig. 7: Sustainability-Technology responses

In this case, because we have the data gaps mentioned above, we chose a simpler approach. We decided to treat the data as a whole, so we created an overall average by multiple counting the overlapping data, thus creating a new universe where our sample data is 3 times larger (in the largest dataset of tested alternatives) compared to the collected data. We tested 6 hypotheses for extracting the average weights with different combinations of:

- Not considering or considering the central intersection - to test the effect of the largest group (about 50% of the total responses, when all other groups exist)
- Not considering or considering double intersections, replacing missing values with:
 - the average size of the remaining universe of double intersections,
 - an average for the given variables within the remaining universe of double intersections

The alternative that best fits the data does not consider the central intersection and considers the double intersections, replacing the missing values with an average for the variables in question in the remaining universe of double intersections. The results are shown in Figure 8.

Fig. 8: Sustainability-Technology results

Next, we analyze the results of question 2, where respondents were asked to rank a list of technologies according to their state of the art. In addition, users could suggest and rank their own technology proposals. We received 72 technology suggestions, of which 49 were unique and some were subsets of our own list. We will not discuss this aspect further.

Fig. 9: Average ranks found.

a) values represent a linear ranking order; b) values represent the actual means calculated

Regarding the ranking of technologies, excluding the user-defined ones in this analysis, we received responses where users did not classify some technologies, although there is a box to drop technologies not considered as STT. We cannot be sure if the unranked technologies were not considered STT, or if it was just a matter of incomplete response or even a combination of the first two situations. To test the impact on the results, we created two separate average ranks, one considering the arithmetic mean and the other considering the

sample mean (see Figure 9). Figure 9 (side "a") shows the ranking in descending order of cutting-edge status, from left to right, taking into account the arithmetic mean rank. It does not show arithmetic averages, but the ranking at equal intervals. In this way, a perfect blue spiral line is obtained, reflecting the steady descent of the ranking.

The number of ranked technologies is different for each technology (yellow line), reflecting the different sample sizes per technology that influence the results. The behavior of the red line, based on the ranking of the samples, follows a spiral in the higher and lower rankings, but in the intermediate rankings, there are several disagreements between approaches. If we analyze the average rank expressed in terms of the arithmetic mean actually calculated (side "b" of 1.8), the differences diminish, although they are still present. This figure expresses the actual distances between the technologies proposed by the respondents in the web application ranking tool and shows that the perceived technological status is close for the divergent ranking categories. This approach also highlights the positive distances between adjacent technologies, e.g. the leap from AI to Augmented Reality is much greater than the leap from the latter to Virtual Reality, and the same effect can be seen between other technologies, although not as pronounced. The highly subjective nature of the field under analysis prevents any further conclusions from being drawn.

In response to question 3, which asked users to rank some of the fundamental principles found in the literature review and to provide their own fundamental principles, we received 13 principle suggestions from 8 users (see Table 3). These propositions reveal important aspects such as tourist mobility or safety.

Table 3: Fundamental principles proposed by respondents

Help tourism destination to be more sustainable, competitive and resilient
Improves mobility efficiency
Enhance the tourist's experience
Metaverse
Creating Tourism Network
Optimise the tourist route
Bring better experience through smart chain management
It supports the improvement of tourism destination branding
It supports the improvement of users' Customer Satisfaction
Promote collaboration among the stakeholders of a tourist destination
Strengthen the governance of the destination
Facilitating tourist mobility around the destination
Increasing security in a tourist destination

With regard to the ranking of the fundamental principles in order of importance, since some principles were not ranked, we followed the same strategy as described above for the technology ranking. In this case, although three fundamental principles change places between the two statistical approaches (although they have similar ranks), the experts were very consensual in their ranking of the fundamental principles of STT (see Figure 10). Interestingly, the results are very similar to those obtained in question 1 on the focus of STT. The tourist and the tourist experience come first, followed by the destination and environmental concerns, and then technological considerations, followed by commercial aspects.

Fig. 10: STT fundamental principles average ranks

We have chosen to use the sample average to construct the Smart Index because we believe it is the most appropriate statistical approach to construct the ranking of ST fundamental principles, as it takes into account the variability and richness of the data collected. This is due to the fact that:

- The sample size is relatively large (334 responses from experts around the world) and representative of different regions, languages and perspectives
- The design of the survey was intuitive, easy, engaging and rewarding, which could have reduced the likelihood of non-response and incomplete answers
- The survey used a rating tool that allowed multiple items in each rating box and the addition or deletion of rating levels at will, which could reflect the experts' preferences and opinions more accurately

Table 4 presents the indices that will be integrated in the final Smartness index.

Table 4: Fundamental principles rank scores

Sentence	sample_mean
Enhance the tourist's emotional, sensorial and/or cognitive experience	0.73
Tailor the tourist experience to each specific user needs	0.70
Bring new opportunities to environmental, responsible, and accessible tourism	0.64
Foster the creation of innovative touristic offers	0.57
Contribute to the tourist socio-cultural enrichment	0.56
Can influence tourist consumption decisions	0.52
Improve the environmental status of the touristic destination	0.51
Improve the economy of the touristic destination	0.51
Improve the social aspects of the touristic destination	0.51
Use cutting-edge technology	0.46
Generate input data for tourism management stakeholders	0.46
Promote the touristic destination	0.44
Improve tourism companies' competitiveness	0.44
Use mainstream technologies in innovative ways	0.43
Simplify tourism companies' operations	0.37
Improve marketing effectiveness	0.36
Scaffold tourism companies' decision making	0.35

Finally, users could write their own definition of STT in an open-ended question. We first used [MAXQDA](#) to help analyze the responses. We started by creating two-word clouds, one with just single words (Figure 11) and the other with bigrams and trigrams (Figure 12).

Fig. 11: Single word word cloud from respondents STT definitions

Once again we can see the importance of the tourist, the destination, and sustainability in the definitions presented. We then coded the responses according to three main categories, (i) STT objectives, (ii) STT target stakeholders, and (iii) technology areas.

Fig. 12: Bigram and trigram word cloud from respondents STT definitions

The code frequency analysis in relation to the STT objectives is shown in Figure 13 (side "a"). Again we see the same pattern as in the previous responses. It is worth noting that some mentions of environmental aspects could be related to broader sustainability, as these two concepts are often used interchangeably, and this was evident in our context analysis. The same could be said for inclusive tourism. The code for this category only highlights responses that specifically mention it, but other mentions of the social aspects of sustainability could also consider this aspect.

Fig. 13: Code frequencies regarding STT. a) goals; b) stakeholders

The analysis of the code frequency regarding the key stakeholders in relation to the STT objectives is presented in Figure 13 (side "b") and again shows the same patterns as previously observed in relation to the STT definition. It should be emphasized that the **stakeholder** code represents the mentions where respondents broadly referred to all direct and indirect stakeholders in the tourism industry. The code frequencies for technology mentions are shown in Figure 14. The code **Technology** refers to mentions of technology as a broad field and does not distinguish between smart and mainstream technologies, i.e.

these could refer to combinations of mainstream and smart technologies, the context analysis points in this direction. The **SMART** code aggregates mentions in different formats such as 'innovative', 'advanced', 'new', or 'cutting edge'. In the code **Mainstream SMART**, respondents specifically mentioned the use of mainstream and/or advanced technologies.

Fig. 14: Code frequencies regarding technology mentions

These results may further support the view of technology presented in the previous question analyses. As one of the respondents put it:

"STT is an integration rather of technology itself, it's a journey not a destination. STT is a set of technology enabled tools which enhance the perceived satisfaction of the travelers by providing faster, convenient and accessible user experience. More than an experience STT is a way towards experiential ecstasy."

In addition, we present an analysis of respondents' definitions of STT, conducted using Bing Chat [Microsoft and OpenAI, 2023], a Large Language Model (LLM). We presented the chatbot with a list of the definitions received and followed up with some questions and answers. The [questions](#) and [answers](#) are presented below.

Q1: On this page, there is a table with the definitions of ST(T) provided by the respondents. You can analyze all the answers in terms of: objectives, stakeholders, technological considerations. In addition, you can highlight the most consensual and the least frequent variables. In addition, you can derive the most consensual definition from those provided.

A1: Here is my analysis of the definitions of ST(T) provided by the respondents:

Objectives: The most common objectives mentioned by the respondents are to enhance the tourism experience, to improve the efficiency and sustainability of tourism, and to create value and benefits for all stakeholders. Some respondents also mention objectives such as innovation, competitiveness, accessibility, inclusivity, and education.

Stakeholders: The most frequently mentioned stakeholders are tourists, tourism providers, destinations, and local communities. Some respondents also mention governments, policymakers, planners, residents, and the environment as stakeholders.

Technological considerations: The most frequently mentioned technologies are ICT, AI, big data, mobile apps, IoT, VR, and AR. Some respondents also mention cloud computing, sensors, wearable devices, smart hotel rooms, service robots, digital twins, and social media as technologies. Some respondents emphasize the importance of personalization, real-time information, data-driven solutions, and user-friendliness as technological features.

The most consensual variables are:

The focus on the tourist and the destination as the main beneficiaries of ST(T).

The emphasis on environmental and societal sustainability as a key objective of ST(T).

The use of a combination of technologies to collect, analyze, and deliver information across the tourism ecosystem.

The least frequent variables are:

The consideration of cultural and historical aspects of tourism destinations.

The involvement of residents and local communities in the co-creation of ST(T).

The evaluation of the impact and performance of ST(T) based on ethical standards and indicators.

Based on the analysis, a possible consensual definition of ST(T) is:

ST(T) are digital tools that use a combination of advanced technologies to provide personalised, interactive, and immersive services for tourists and other stakeholders. They also aim to improve the efficiency, quality, and competitiveness of tourism operations and products. ST(T) should be aligned with the principles and goals of sustainable tourism, considering the environmental and societal impacts on the destination and its local community.

The answer is very much in line with our own analysis of the data, with the greatest consensus around improving the tourist experience and the efficiency and sustainability of tourism. It is curious to note that the definition provided by the model refers to the use of advanced technologies, although this is not mentioned in any of the data presented by the model earlier. As this aspect was somewhat at odds with our own analysis, we asked further questions.

Q2: Regarding technological mentions, what is the frequency of respondents who mention advanced technologies, the frequency of mentions that mention the use of traditional and

advanced technologies and, finally, the frequency of responses in which no "intelligence" status is mentioned, i.e. mentions of technology in general.

A2: Based on the current web page context, here is my analysis of the technological mentions in the definitions of STT provided by the respondents:

The frequency of respondents who mention advanced technologies, such as AI, VR, AR, IoT, big data, etc., is 54 out of 160 (33.75%).

The frequency of respondents who mention the use of both traditional and advanced technologies, such as ICT, mobile apps, cloud computing, etc., is 42 out of 160 (26.25%).

The frequency of respondents who do not mention any specific technology or "intelligence" status, but use general terms such as technology, innovation, digital, etc., is 64 out of 160 (40%).

The analysis of the nature of technology mentions is consistent with our own conclusions. It should be noted that LLMs are not particularly good at statistical analysis per se at this stage, so we should not take the figures provided as absolute truth, although they are very powerful in semantic, content, context, and sentiment analysis.

We also asked for widely varying definitions.

Q3: Are there widely divergent definitions?

A3: Based on the current web page context, there is a high level of consensus among the respondents on the main objectives, stakeholders, and technological considerations of STT. However, there are also some divergent definitions and perspectives on certain aspects of STT. For example, some respondents emphasize the importance of cultural and historical aspects of tourism destinations, while others focus more on the environmental and societal impacts. Some respondents also have different views on the role of residents and local communities in the co-creation of STT, as well as the evaluation of the impact and performance of STT based on ethical standards and indicators.

Overall, while there is a high level of consensus among experts on the main objectives, stakeholders, and technological considerations of STT, there are also some divergent definitions and perspectives on certain aspects of STT, particularly with regard to how these principles and goals are interpreted and implemented by different experts. These differences reflect the complexity and diversity of the tourism industry, as well as the need for a multi-disciplinary and collaborative approach to the development and implementation of STT.

Although there may be some divergent opinions on certain aspects of STT, this response does not reflect the existence of obvious divergences in the responses, at most their complementarity.

We also provided Bing GPT with the raw data for the other questions, explaining the structure of the data and asking for an analysis of the different questions, and to analyse the consensus between the definition classification question and the Venn diagrams. LLM's analysis was in line with our previous conclusions.

We are now performing Natural Language Processing (NLP) using LLMs to extract the relevant data needed for the statistical analysis that will allow us to derive the final weights from this section, which will integrate the Observatory's Smartness Index.

- Discussion

ST refers to the use of technology and data-based solutions to improve the tourist experience, destination management, and sustainability. It involves the collaboration of different stakeholders, such as tourists, suppliers, governments, and residents, to create value and benefits for all. ST is inspired by the concept of smart cities but also takes into account the specific needs and characteristics of tourism and tourism destinations.

STTs are the set of tools that support the development and implementation of smart tourism. In this sense STT:

- (i) apply the fundamental principles of ST, to achieve (at least some of) the ST goals,
- (ii) within the specific scope envisioned by the developers (the domain of the application and the specificities of the final consumer or area, ensuring the concordance with ST scope),
- (iii) considering the inputs of/and the final influence on the key stakeholders,
- (iv) taking advantage of the relationship of their specific field, the ST field (as most STT developers are not specifically working with ST, but are experts in their own field, e.g. VR), and with other interconnected knowledge areas, either technological or not, while applying techniques and technologies and,
- (v) trying to minimize biases at an operational level (e.g. avoid search engine "commercial" algorithmic influence in AI-based tourism recommendation systems) and on a conceptual level, ensuring that the STT are actually STT and not merely digital tools.

Our proposed consensual definition for STT is that of seamlessly interconnected digital tools designed to benefit all stakeholders in the tourism industry, with a special focus on the tourist and the destination, that aim at local, and possibly global, sustainable development. At their

highest level, STTs produce experiential ecstasy in the dynamic human interface with technology, enriching and not alienating people. At decreasing smartness levels they also aim to improve the efficiency, quality, and competitiveness of tourism destinations, operations, products, and companies.

The level of Smartness of STT depends more on achieving the objectives of sustainable tourism than on their technological status. Of course, emerging technologies offer unforeseen possibilities, but so does innovation combined with conventional technology. This means that the intelligence of these tools (as long as they contain technological solutions) should be assessed on the basis of their alignment with the principles and objectives of sustainable tourism. A full evaluation would require assessing the results of implementing the tools, i.e. their impact on all stakeholders in the tourism industry (considering the different levels of importance found in the study) and on local (and possibly global) sustainability (again considering the different levels of importance found in the study).

This last (more complete) Smartness assessment is outside the scope of this project, as it is impossible to carry out a proper impact assessment at the level we are working on. Our proposed Smartness assessment is based solely on the potential impact of STTs based on the information available, mainly in the product descriptions and then in more detailed descriptions provided by the developers/owners.

2.2.3 STT operational taxonomy

We analysed the STTs offered in the above-mentioned STT catalogues ([Gidlund and McGurren, 2020], [Scholz & Friends Agenda, 2022], [SEGITTUR Turismo e Innovación, 2022]) and the descriptions of STTs offered on the Internet, trying to map the areas of operation of STTs, the types of STTs available and the types of technology most commonly used. This allowed us to identify three areas of application for STTs. In this sense, STTs can be:

- Tools as (part of) the tourist offer - they are part of the tourist experience and in some cases, they constitute the complete tourist experience.
- Tools for marketing the tourist offer
- Tools for the management and operation of tourism products and/or destinations.

These domains are not exclusive, i.e. some STTs operate in several domains.

Regarding the existing types of STT, we found 10 different (non-exclusive) classes. The main

difference between them is not a technological consideration, but rather the differences on the final objectives proposed by the developers and the domains in which they operate. (see Table 5).

Table 5: proposed STT operational taxonomy

ACTION DOMAIN	STT TYPE	DESCRIPTION
(Part of) the touristic offer	Fully digital experience	STT corresponding to a tourism experience occurring in the virtual world (e.g., virtual tours).
	Partial digital experience	STT enables and/or enriches the tourist experience in the real world with additional and registered digital content (e.g., augmented reality tours).
	Building block	Scaffolding tools that support the enrichment of the tourist experience (e.g., audio or video content creation).
Marketing	Pre-consumption	STT is employed in the pre-consumption stage, where tourists engage in the decision-making process, and where motivations and expectations are formed (e.g., selecting and booking the destination and corresponding touristic services).
	Consumption	STT is employed in the consumption stage (aka "service encounter" stage), where tourists enjoy the preselected touristic services.
	Post-consumption	STT is employed in the post-consumption stage, where tourists act as influencers of further users of the selected touristic services (e.g., sharing feelings raised and/or contents created during the consumption stage).
Management & Operations	Design of tourism products	STT aimed at helping in the creation of touristic offers (e.g., B2B platforms helping build tourism packages).
	Deployment of tourism products	STT assists in the deployment of touristic offers (e.g., online booking and payment platforms).
	Operation of tourism products	STT assists in the operation of touristic offerings (e.g., crowd management tools).
	Maintenance/evolution of tourism products	STT helps in the evaluation and decision-making regarding the existing touristic offer (e.g., data analytics tools).

In addition, we have compiled the technological areas that make up the tools analyzed. A non-exhaustive list is presented in Figure 15, that tries to map the technological areas in the cognition areas of the human brain.

Fig. 15: Technologies most commonly found in STT

2.3 Final remarks

The domains of action compiled cover all the areas of application found not only in the literature review, but also in the responses to the web application form and form the backbone of the STT taxonomy that will integrate the European Observatory's Smartness Index.

Combining this with the insights from our participatory approach, we plan to develop a smartness index for STT, using the data derived from the survey results as its core. This index should take into account the specific goals of STT, the technological and implementation aspects, the potential impact on local (and global) sustainability, and the existence of stakeholder involvement and considerations.

3. Reifying the observatory

3.1. Platform selection

3.1.1. *Virtual tradeshow option*

Our initial intention for hosting the observatory was a virtual trade fair platform with customizable 3D booths. The chosen platform should meet the following requirements:

- be developed by a company based in the EU, since the observatory is part of a European project
- be indexed and optimized for search engine optimization (SEO)
- have an Application Programming Interface (API) that allows: creating new users as the observatory grows, creation of virtual stands, upload user information and stand data, and add custom classification fields for each booth
- the platform/company must be stable to guarantee the online permanence required by an Observatory (365/24 and 24/7)
- visitors do not need to register
- the platform's business model must have the option of buying a license at a fixed price, and not depending on the use of the platform
- each STT has to be presented in an individual booth with independent access. In other words, the company responsible for the STT only has editing permissions with its stand
- the layout of the fair should be configurable to allow grouping of related STTs

After analysing the available online offer, most products were discarded for not meeting our criteria, notably because most companies in this market aim at closed events and do not provide access to search engines. Some companies provide turnkey solutions, not allowing for user customizations/booth creation, and most offers are located in Asia or the US.

We met with two EU-based companies [Swapcard](#), and [Fairsnext](#), and despite our best efforts, we were never able to meet with [meetyoo](#) and [Virtual Booth](#). [Swapcard](#) was discarded as it did not offer 3D solutions. Regarding [Fairsnext](#), although it met most of our requirements and we developed an initial prototype in the platform we ruled it out after discovering that their API doesn't allow automatic creation of stands. It is only possible to create them manually (we tried automating the virtual stand upload tool available in the platform but without success).

3.1.2. Omeka choice rationale

Due to the previously identified limitations, we decided to use the [Omeka Net \(gold\)](#) platform. As it says on its website, “Omeka is a web publishing platform for sharing digital collections and creating media-rich online exhibits”. Instead of being an experience at a virtual fair with 3D booths, it is similar to visiting a website, and Omeka gives us the stability of a mature project, been online since 2007.

3.2. Data sources

Table 6: Selected data sources

ID	Origin	Description	# STTs
[Gidlund and McGurran, 2020]	TravelTech for Scotland	“This Toolkit started out as part of a project to help tourism in Scotland recover after the COVID-19 crisis. It was created by tourism professionals during 6 weeks in spring 2020, and the first edition was published in June 2020.”	27
[Scholz & Friends Agenda, 2022]	European Commission	“The purpose of this document is to enhance and facilitate the exchange of best practices in promoting innovative and smart measures and initiatives for tourism destinations in the EU Member States. The report aims at raising awareness about smart tourism tools, measures and projects, sharing the best practices in tourism implemented by cities and strengthening peer-to-peer learning and innovative development of tourism in the EU in general.”	145
[SEGITTUR Turismo e Innovación, 2022]	Spain's Secretary of State for Tourism	“This edition includes a total of 252 solutions and services, all categorized in line with the key areas of Smart. The Destination model is based on: governance, sustainability, innovation, technology and accessibility. The Covid-19 category has been added to these five main areas, to classify the solutions that enable work to be carried out in this environment.”	252

3.3. Extract, Transform, and Load (ETL)

As defined by [Nwokeji and Matovu, 2021], ETL is a data integration approach that involves three phases (data extraction, transformation and loading). The authors performed a systematic literature review (SLR) to provide a critical perspective on the state of research in ETL from 2006 onwards. They followed the methodology proposed in [Kitchenham and Charters, 2007] and defined four review questions in line with the review objectives:

- RQ1: What are the techniques or approaches used for implementing ETL workflows or processes?
- RQ2: What are the quality attributes to be considered when selecting ETL solutions?
- RQ3: What are the prevailing challenges in developing ETL solutions?
- RQ4: What is the current depth of coverage in ETL research with respect to the application domain, geographical locations, and frequency of papers published?

Table 7: Common ETL techniques and approaches

Approach	Description	Type	ETL Stage(s)
Conceptual modeling	Consists of defining the entities and relationships involved in the data flow, as well as the rules and constraints that govern the transformation of data from source to target.	Framework	All stages
Domain ontology	It provides a shared vocabulary and a set of concepts, relationships, and rules that can be the basis for modeling and understanding the data within that domain.	Framework	Extraction and Transformation
Web-based	Involves using web-based tools and services to simplify data management strategies and improve data quality by providing a standardised approach to intake, sharing, and storage.	Technique	All stages
Parallelization	Is the use of parallel processing techniques to speed up ETL processes. This approach can reduce system memory footprint and take full advantage of the computing power of multi-core processors.	Technique	All stages
Multi-agent system (MAS)	Can be summarised as the interaction between multiple agents within an environment to solve problems.	Framework	All stages
Metadata repository	Automate and streamline the ETL process with the stored information, providing transparency and traceability for data lineage and quality.	Technique	All stages
Structured Query Languages (SQL)	Management of data in databases using SQL commands.	Technique	Transformation and Loading
Service Oriented Architecture (SOA)	Refers to an architectural approach that involves using loosely coupled and reusable software components to perform ETL processes. These components, known as services, can be developed and deployed independently, allowing for greater flexibility and scalability in the ETL process.	Framework	All stages
Fault-tolerant algorithm	An algorithm designed to be fault-tolerant, which means it can continue to function even when errors or failures occur.	Technique	All stages

Table 7 shows the techniques or approaches identified by the authors as the most widely used today to implement ETL workflows or processes. In addition, we have provided our description to facilitate understanding of the concepts involved. Since the authors presented techniques for implementing ETL workflows alongside conceptual frameworks, we added a "Type" column for discrimination purposes. Frameworks provide general guidelines for designing and implementing ETL processes, while techniques are specific methods used to implement certain aspects of an ETL solution. We have also added another column identifying the ETL phases to which each approach applies.

Table 8 describes the quality attributes to consider when creating ETL solutions, again in order from most to least mentioned (definitions taken from the above article):

Table 8: Quality attributes to consider when creating ETL solutions

Quality attribute	Definition
Flexibility	Refers to the ability of an ETL solution to accommodate changes in data integration requirements.
Performance	This implies that the ETL process must be completed within a specified time window and the functional mapping of data from source to target must be correct.
Reusability	Defines the ability of an ETL solution to be used in various application domains.
Data quality	Refers to the degree to which data produced by an ETL solution is fit for use.
Scalability	Defines the ability of ETL solutions to be used for data of varying volumes and complexities.
Interoperability	Implies that ETL solutions should support the integration of data from heterogeneous operational data sources, irrespective of technological, syntactic, and semantic schemas.
Reliability	Is the probability that the ETL solution will not fail to perform its intended functions within the specified time.
Fault-tolerance	The ability of ETL solutions to function optimally in the presence of fault.

The most recurrent challenges identified in descending order are complexity, time-consuming, data heterogeneity, cost, lack of automation, standardization issues, and maintenance.

It should be noted that the authors of the article were unable to explain “*why existing research underemphasizes the importance of fault-tolerance both as an approach to developing ETL solutions and a desirable quality attribute for ETL solutions. Equally, reliability is another quality attribute that received less attention from existing studies*”

○

3.4. Smart ETL

3.4.1. Introduction

As previously analyzed for the case of STT, “Smart” is a fuzzy concept. In the case of ETL, we are applying the term as an extension of traditional ETL with the very powerful capabilities of AI in semantic, content, contextual analysis, and text extraction. In the ETL data integration approach, we use LLMs, i.e., models similar to ChatGPT. However, LLMs will only bring developments, particularly in terms of efficiency because they will automate some tasks, in the Extraction and Transformation phases and the Data Classification process. In the loading phase, using these models won't add anything new.

3.4.2. Text Extraction and Image Extraction

For extracting text and images from websites, PDFs, and other sources we used Python open-source libraries, such as [PyPDF2](#) and [pdfminer](#) for text extraction and [PyMuPDF](#) for image extraction from PDFs. For web scrapping, we are using the [BeautifulSoup](#) library.

3.4.3. Smart contents extraction

Much of the process of extracting useful information from the text obtained in the text extraction stage is automated by using LLMs. The same can be done with the resulting images, but that is not where we are focused. Full automation is not feasible at this point because it is necessary to instruct the model to differentiate between what information is wanted and what is not. This process of instructing, better known as creating a prompt, is one of the biggest challenges we face. Although several Prompt Engineering courses teach good practices for creating a good prompt (e.g. the free [DeepLearning.AI](#) course), it is still necessary to use the trial and error method to obtain the best prompt for each case. We are striving to reach the ideal prompt to find out if the product or service described is an STT. must be in line with the results of our study presented in section 2. STT taxonomy. We consider two strategies to provide this knowledge to the LLM:

- prompt engineering;
- using embeddings² to provide the LLM with a pre-context while evaluating the possible STTs. For this, we intend to use [Quivr](#) (described below).

² Embeddings are numerical representations of information, such as text, images, audio, etc. [They capture the semantic meaning of what is being embedded and make it easier to do machine learning on large inputs. For example, word embeddings are vectors that represent the meaning of words](#)

If a product qualifies as an STT, then we aim at extracting:

- STT name;
- STT description;
- Producers/developers info, including geographical location;
- URL containing additional information;
- **STT characterization variables** - the information collected in this stage will allow us to rank the different STTs in terms of Smartness:
 - STT type and the respective domain(s),
 - Technological fields used,
 - STT definition rank,
 - Sustainable development goal(s) declared in the text or that can be inferred from it (here we might need to provide examples to the LLM, increasing its understanding of the task);
 - STT target/focus.

As a prompting strategy, we are considering Tree of Thoughts (ToT) prompting as it [substantially outperforms other prompting methods](#). ToT, proposed in [Hulbert, 2023], is a framework that generalizes over [Chain-of-Thought \(CoT\) prompting](#) [Wei et al., 2023] and encourages exploration over thoughts that serve as intermediate steps for general problem-solving with language models. ToT prompting applies the main concept from ToT frameworks as a simple prompting technique, getting the LLM to evaluate intermediate thoughts in a single prompt, and is described by its author as follows:

“Identify and behave as three different experts that are appropriate to answering this question.

All experts will write down the step and their thinking about the step, then share it with the group.

Then, all experts will go on to the next step, etc.

At each step all experts will score their peers response between 1 and 5, 1 meaning it is highly unlikely, and 5 meaning it is highly likely.

If any expert is judged to be wrong at any point then they leave.

After all experts have provided their analysis, you then analyse all 3 analyses and provide either the consensus solution or your best guess solution.

The question is... ”

As far as the geographical area is concerned, it is necessary to explore the URLs in the catalogues, since in most cases there is no information there about this. This is a pending task that will require web crawling and scrapping. Nevertheless, the biggest challenge we are facing now is finding a way to have enough computational power to explore an LLM. Being able to use an LLM without third-party services, such as [OpenAI API](#), is the ideal solution, and to achieve this we need to run the model on a computer or server that is controlled by

trusted parties. We tried unsuccessfully to run open-source models (like [Meta Llama 2](#)) on the [ISTAR-IUL](#) (Information Sciences, Technologies, and Architecture Research Center) server equipped with a powerful GPU board (NVIDIA GPU RTX 3090). Our next alternative was using [Google Colab](#), which allows us to write and execute Python code on a browser, and our academic credentials gave us access to some premium features, like more powerful GPUs, RAM, and computer storage space. This option was not feasible either, due to a shortage of RAM. We then concluded that for a model like this to fully deploy its value, a high-performance computer is mandatory.

In mitigation, our current non-optimal solution (because availability is not guaranteed in the medium to long term) is using the [Python library hugchat](#), which acts as an unofficial API for [HuggingFace's HuggingChat](#) service (a free online platform that makes the community's best AI chat models available to everyone). This library was created by independent programmers, and it is possible to see HuggingFace CTO's thanks for this project on the project's [GitHub page](#). This solution allowed us to access good LLMs and test our program.

We are also currently exploring the [Quivr](#) project whose GitHub page describes itself as “*Your Second Brain supercharged by Generative AI*”. The idea is to pre-upload files in different formats to gain knowledge about the domain in question. After that, we can ask questions about that domain in a style identical to the chat models we know. Here, we have two options to use LLMs:

- **Local:** In this case, we have the problem of a lack of computing power.
- **Through an API:** Instead of using the commercial OpenAI API, we customized it to use the previously mentioned non-optimal *HuggingChat API*.

We will continue to look for alternatives as we improve our program, as the solution of using LLMs via APIs is not ideal.

All code developed in the scope of the STT Observatory is available as open-source in our [RESETTING GitHub repository](#). A mock-up of the STT Observatory is available at [this link](#).

4. Observatory dissemination and continuity

4.1. Observatory dissemination

The dissemination of the observatory will be targeted to two different audiences:

- (i) exiting European producers of STTs;
- (ii) potential European consumers of STTs, namely European tourism SMEs seeking digital transformation opportunities.

As for the European producers of STTs, our initial set will be the ones identified in the aforementioned data sources (the catalogues of STTs). They will be contacted to assess their willingness to be represented in the observatory. Upon their acceptance, they should check for the correctness and completeness of the automatically retrieved contents and perform all required updates. In communicating with European SMEs to foster their participation in the STT observatory (to be developed in the scope of Task 3.2), namely inviting them to perform a self-assessment on their digital readiness. Furthermore, we plan to disseminate the first version of this observatory at the [TIS \(Tourism Innovation Summit\)](#) meeting to be held on 18-20 October in Seville, Spain.

4.2. Observatory continuity

Iscte has a long tradition of hosting [observatories in Social Sciences](#) fields, such as the Inequality Observatory, Emigration Observatory, European Observatory of Working Life, European Employment Observatory, and the Observatory of Families and Family Policy. We expect the **European STT Observatory** to be the first one in the scope of [Iscte's School of Technology and Architecture](#).

To guarantee the continuity of the European STT observatory beyond the duration of the RESETTING project, we have prospects to obtain financial support from [NEST Tourism Innovation Center](#) and [Turismo de Portugal](#), the National Tourism Authority, operating under the auspices of the Ministry for the Economy and Digital Transition, as well as establish contacts with European hubs specialized in tourism innovation to assess their interest in joining efforts.

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